

earthone

Environmental **A**nalysis and **R**esilience
for **T**ransformative **H**uman-**O**ptimised
Natural **E**nvironments

6 pilots in **Croatia, Greece, Italy, North Macedonia, Slovenia, and Spain** for improved land use management across Europe

Afforestation

Land use change management practices/agroforestry

Organic soils: rewetting/ extensivisation

Forest management/ better use of wood biomass

Efficient fertilizer use

Dietary changes

Agriculture/ pasture

17

PARTNERS

1

SHARED VISION

10

COUNTRIES

STAY IN TOUCH

earthone-project.eu

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID

